

Sample Name: Nanotalc Milled

Material: Talc

Size: <1 μm

Production Partner: Nanoshel

Storage Conditions: Refrigerated and dark

Structure

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- 81% particles are <1 μm
- Particles have a sharp, flake morphology with angular corners
- $4.0 \pm 0.09 \cdot 10^{11}$ particles per gram
- $11920 \pm 150 \text{ cm}^2/\text{g}$ surface area
- Milled talc has a slightly larger average particle size than unmilled talc, possibly due to agglomeration

Chemical Characteristics

- P, Ca, Fe, Cl and Zr were the most abundant contaminants, all <500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
 - Contaminants total 1156 $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$

Description of terms

- $D[4,3]$: Volume mean (μm)
- $D[3,2]$: Surface area mean (μm)
- $D[2,1]$: Spherical particle mean (μm)
- $D[1,0]$: Number length mean (μm)
- D_V : Median diameter (volume basis, μm)
- D_N : Median diameter (number basis, μm)
- N_w : Number of particles per gram plastic (#/g)
- A_w : Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm^2/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using Static Light Scattering (SLS) provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D _v	D _N	N _w	A _w
2.9±0.2	1.8±0.02	1.2±0.01	0.81±0.00	1.2±0.01	0.81±0.00	4.0±0.09 10 ¹¹	11920±150

Morphology (using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) provided by TNO)

Chemical Composition (using XRF provided by Malvern Panalytical)

Component	Concentration (µg/g)
P	467
Ca	251
Fe	179
Cl	118
Zr	106
Cr	15
Y	9
Ti	4
Ni	4
Mn, Cu, Zn	<2

**Quantification calculated based on oxide structure, Mg and Si concentrations*